

**XIV-XV ASR TARIXIGA OID MANBALARNI A.O'RINBOEV
TADQIQOTLARIDA AKS ETISHI**

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Annotasiya: XIV-XV asrlar Amir Temur va temuriylar davlati tarixiga oid bo'lib, bu davr manbalari asosan arab tilida yaratilgan. Ularni ilmiy muomalaga kiritishda A.O'rinboevning xizmatlari va tadqiqotlari qisqacha yoritildi.

Kalit so'zlar: Tarix, manba, mamlakat, siyosat, ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, madaniy hayot.

Аннотация: XIV-XV века относятся к истории Амира Темура и государства Тимуридов, причем источники этого периода написаны преимущественно на арабском языке. Кратко освещались заслуги и исследования А. Уринбоева при их введении в научный оборот.

Ключевые слова: История, источник, страна, политика, социальная, экономическая, культурная жизнь.

Abstract: The 14th-15th centuries refer to the history of Amir Temur and the Timurid state, and the sources of this period are written mainly in Arabic. The merits and research of A. Urinboev were briefly highlighted when they were introduced into scientific circulation.

Key words: History, source, country, politics, social, economic, cultural life.

Har bir suveren davlat o'zining betakror tarixi va madaniyatiga egadir. Bu tarix, bu madaniyatning haqiqiy ijodkori, yaratuvchisi esa haqli ravishda shu mamlakat xalqi xisoblanadi-deb ta'kidlagan mamlakatimiz prezidenti

SH.M.Mirziyoev [1.1.]. Davlatimiz tom ma'noda mustaqil bo'lganidan keyin xalqimiz ijtimoiy-siyosiy, iqtisodiy, madaniy hayotida tubdan o'zgarishlar bo'ldi. O'zbek xalqining necha ming yillik tarixida qanday murakkab davrlar, og'ir sinovlar bo'lganini barchamiz yaxshi bilamiz. O'zbek davlatchilik tarixi dunyo tarixchi olimlari tomonidan katta qiziqish bilan o'rganilayotgan bir vaqtda sovet tarixchilari tomonidan yurtimiz tarixi salbiy bo'rttirilgan holda talqin etilgan.

Sovet mafkurasi sabab, O'zbekiston tarixini xolis yoritishga bo'lgan to'siqlar avj olgan, xaqiqiy tarixchi olimlar uchun og'ir vaqtlar bo'lishiga qaramay akademik YAxyo G'ulomov, I.Mo'minov, B.Axmedov, taniqli manbashunos A.O'rinboev va boshqa zabardast tarixchi olimlar o'zlarining maqsadlari sari olg'a borishlik bilan ma'naviy jasorat ko'rsatib bugungi yoshlarga namuna bo'lib qoldilar.

O'zbekiston tarixini o'rganishda katta hissa qo'shgan har bir olimning xayoti va ilmiy merosi doimo insonda qiziqish uyg'otadi. Ayniqsa, A.O'rinboev bir vaqtning o'zida o'zbek, rus, arab, fors tillarini mukammal biluvchi yetuk tarixchi olim, sharqshunos, fidoiy pedagog, jamoat arbobi, Abu Rayhon Beruniy nomidagi Davlat mukofoti sohibi[2.1.], oliyjanob inson sifatida bugungi kunda O'zbekiston tarixi fanida yoshlar xavas qilsa arziydigan shaxs sifatida yodga olinadi va olimning ilmiy merosini o'rganish zaruratini tug'diradi. Bugungi kunda O'zbekiston tarixini rivojiga o'z xizmatini qo'shgan olimlar ilmiy merosini tadqiq etish va buni yoshlarga o'rgatish milliy o'zlikni anglashdagi bir vazifa xisoblanadi.

Amir Temur va Temuriylar davlati tarixi, XIV-XV asrlarda Markaziy Osiyo hududlarda yashagan xalqlarning siyosiy, ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, madaniy hayotidan ma'lumot beruvchi manbalar tadqiqi A.O'rinboev ilmiy faoliyatida markaziy o'rinni egallagan. Bu yo'nalish ham mazmunan turli fasllarga bo'linadi:

-1991 yilda A. O'rinboev "G'iyosiddin Naqqoshning Xitoy safarnomasi" nomli ilmiy tadqiqotini yakunlab, nashr ettirdi [3.1.]. Temuriylar davlatining diplomatik aloqalari, elchilik munosabatlari tarixidan ma'lumot beruvchi qimmatli bu manbaning alohida hususiyati shundan iboratki, u Xitoy davlati haqida to'la

ma'lumot olish mumkin bo'lgan yagona qo'lyozma sifatida tarix fanida o'z o'rniga egadir. Unda Temuriylardan bo'lgan hukmdorlarning Xitoy davlatiga yuborgan elchilari va elchilik munosabatlarini xronologik va xududiy xaritasi va safarga oid qiziqarli tarixiy ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Ushbu elchilar 1420 yil favral oyining 25-sanasida Xitoy elchilari bilan birga Samarqand shahridan yo'lga tushgan bo'lib, Toshkent, Sayram va Ashpara hududlaridan o'tib, Mo'g'uliston hududiga 25-aprelda yetib boradi.

Bu vaqtda Mo'g'ulistonda siyosiy kelishmovchiliklar kuchaygan, Uvaysxon bilan SHer Muhammad O'g'lon oralarida adovat yuzaga kelgan bir davr bo'lgan. Siyosiy notinch hududga kirgan Temuriylar saltanati elchilari tabiiyki, sarosimada bo'ladi. Ammo, Mo'g'ulistonda katta mavqega ega bo'lgan dug'lat amirlaridan Hudoydod elchilar ularni oldiga kelib, hech qanday xavf hatar yo'qligi, safarlarini bemalol davom ettirishlarini aytadi. SHundan keyingina elchilar 1420 yilning 10 iyunida YUlduz yayloviga, 1420 yilning 11 iyulida Turfonga, 16 iyulida Qoraxoja hududlariga yetib boradilar. Xitoy imperatori tomonidan yuborilgan maxsus guruh 21-iyulda kelib elchilarni kutib oladi, ya'ni nomlarini yozib olishadi. SHundan keyin Temuriylarning elchilari Xitoy davlati va fuqarolari tomonidan ijobiy kutib olinadi. U yerdagi elchilik munosabatlari G'iyosiddin Naqqosh tomonidan qayd etib borilgan. Uning ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, SHohrux tomonidan yuborilgan elchilar Xitoy imperatori tomonidan katta hurmat va e'tibor bilan kutib olingan [4.1.]. SHohrux Mirzo va uning amirlarining Xitoy hukmdoriga yo'llagan maktublari bir parcha sariq atlasga o'rab, imperatorga taqdim etiladi. Xitoyga yuborilgan Temuriylar elchilari 1422 yili Hirotga yetib kelgan. Bu elchilik munosabatlari natijasida asosiy e'tibor savdo-iqtisodiy munosabatlarga qaratilganligi uchun, mamlakatlar o'rtasidagi ichki va tashqi savdo rivojlangan.

A.O'rinboev 1991 yilda XIV asr oxiri XV asr boshlarida O'rta Osiyoda qurilish va obidalar tarixiga oid qimmatli ma'lumotlarni o'zida ja'mlagan maqolani nashr ettirgan. Ushbu maqolaga asos sifatida SHarafiddin Ali YAzdiyning **Vol. 2. Issue 4**

“Zafarnoma” asari olingan[5.1.]. A.O'rinboevning ushbu maqolasi arxitektura va bino inshootlari qurilishi sohasidagi olimlar uchun ham foydali tadqiqot bo'lib xizmat qilmoqda.

Mustaqillikdan so'ng Temur va Temuriylar davlati tarixiga xolis baho berilar ekan, 1994 yilda temuriy shahzodalardan biri, astronom olim mirzo Ulug'bekning 600 yillik yubileyi munosabati bilan ilmiy tadbirlar tashkil etildi va o'tkazildi. Ayni shu munosabat bilan A.O'rinboev ham o'z ilmiy tadqiqoti bilan ko'plab jurnal va ilmiy-anjumanlarda faol qatnashdi [6.1.]. Ushbu maqolalarning biri fransuz tilida, biri rus tilida, yana biri esa o'zbek tilida nashr etilganligi olimning lingvistik erudiyasini yuqori bo'lganligiga dalolatdir.

A.O'rinboevning naqshbandiya ta'limoti tarixiga oid ilmiy izlanishlari ham mavjud bo'lib, ularda Islom dinining turli ta'riqatlaridan farqli ravishda naqshbandiya tariqatining rivojlanishi va uning namoyondalari haqida qimmatli ma'lumotlar keltiriladi. Masalan, 1994 yilda nashr qilingan “XV asr yozishmalarida naqshbandiya ta'limotining aks etishi” nomli maqolasida ushbu ta'limotning yirik namoyondalaridan Abdurahmon Jomiy, Alisher Navoiy, Husayn Boyqaro, Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur kabilar haqida so'z borgan. Ayniqsa, Abdurahmon Jomiy va Alisher Navoiy maktublarida “Dast ba koru dil ba YOr” shiori ostida rivojlangan naqshbandiya ta'limotining “Xilvat dar anjuman, safar dar vatan, nazar bar qadam, hush dar dam” kabi qoidalarining bayoni haqida qiziqarli ma'lumotlar berilgan[7.1.]. Ushbu tariqat nomi Bahouddin Naqshbandiy bilan bog'liqligi sir emas.

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